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e i ragionamenti morali e che completano la natura umana nella realizzazione della sua libertà.

L'ultimo articolo del compendio è *Conceptual Connections: Kant and the Twentieth-Century Analytic Tradition* di James O'Shea. Egli sottolinea come le figure fondative dei principali movimenti della filosofia analitica, da Frege a Russell, da Moore a Wittgenstein e il pragmatismo americano hanno definito la loro filosofia in rapporto diretto con la rivoluzione copernicana di Kant. Se dopo il Neo-kantismo, la posizione della filosofia analitica era quella di rifiuto delle posizioni di Kant, durante la seconda metà del ventesimo secolo con le opere di Sellars e di Strawson si ha un rinnovato interesse per l'opera kantiana. L'influenza esercitata da Kant è individuata da O'Shea in quattro temi principali: 1) il problema dei giudizi sintetici a priori; 2) la rivoluzione copernicana secondo cui gli oggetti si conformano al soggetto; 3) le condizioni a priori della possibilità dell'esperienza; 4) l'idealismo trascendentale come opposizione fra noumeni e fenomeni.

Marco Sgarbi

Francesco Berto, *Che cosa è la dialettica hegeliana. Un'interpretazione analitica del metodo*, Il Poligrafo, Padua 2005. Un volume di pp. 453.

Although the past century has witnessed a number of attempts at providing an exhaustive commentary of the *Science of Logic*, such attempts were in most cases, however, contaminated by either the wish of recovering social or anthropological aspects within dialectical dynamism or that of providing its formalization. Only a handful of scholars have considered Hegel's dialectical logic with a regard to both metaphysics and analytic philosophy, for which reason Berto's book fills a gap. It obviously goes back to Robert Brandom's analytic re-contextualization of Hegel. On the other side, though, Berto takes distance from Brandom's conceptual pragmatism and proposes instead an interpretation of dialectic as a general theory of meaning.

The introduction focuses on methodological problems. Berto lays out sources and arguments that speak against the possibility of an analytic reading of Hegel (p. 33). The first chapter of the first part, on logic and dialectic, aims at dismissing Popper's claim that dialectic be conflicting and therefore inconsistent. Berto questions the validity the major of Popper's argument, which says that all conflicting theories

are inconsistent. He maintains instead that it is good for dialectic to deny the principle of non-contradiction for dialectic requires exactly what Popper was claiming he was missing, namely a reconsideration of the semantics of descriptive terms (p. 75). The last two chapters of the first part examine the Hegel-critiques formulated by formal logicians and show that the attacks were either flatly wrong or right, but only in some ways. Berto considers erroneous the positions that presuppose Hegel to have picked some insufficiencies of the logical tradition and to have introduced some peculiar formal properties instead, e.g. Alfred Tarski, John N. Findlay, Slawomir Rogowski, Arend Kullenkampff, Leo Apostel, and Graham Priest, Berto contends that for these logicians Hegel has tried to provide an extension of classic logic, which is absurd, given Hegel's non-classical approach (p. 101). Right, but in some ways are the interpretations in terms of para-consistent logic of Stanisław Jaśkowski, Ernst F. F. Zermelo, Adolf Fraenkel, Willard V. O. Quine, Enrico Berti, Richard Routley, and Newton C. A. da Costa who agree with Hegel that some contradictions yield truths (p. 139).

The five chapters of the second part, in which Berto proposes his own interpretation of dialectic as a form of semantics delve into Hegel's *sich aufhebender Widerspruch* and his fundamental notion that all things underlie the form of a judgment and of a syllogism. Berto sees dialectic holistically as a general theory of meaning. A subject (A), according to Berto's reading of Hegel, is the carrier of a general meaning, so that its relation to the meanings carried by other subjects is essential and necessary in as far as the relation to other subjects determines and individuates the original meaning. It is the meaning's determinacy—so Berto—that identifies the conditions of identity for which things are what they are. Dialectic takes up the role, then, of an individualational holism. The triple movement of dialectic takes up the following structure. 1) the abstractive intellect conceive the subject A, which is meant as some meaning in necessary relation with another meaning B, whereby B is necessary to the individuation and determination of A. A and B therefore are not anymore conceivable in and for themselves. 2) By the consideration of A and B the understanding cannot help producing a failure of determinacy that creates a contradiction. For as long as A is conceived identically for itself while at the same time it is conceived for another B, the result is that we deal with an A' and an A'', that are completely different. 3) The third moment takes place at the level of reason, a level before which Kant choose to stop. A comprehends now its opposite in its unity, i.e., the positive in

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the negative and thus also the unity of the determinations in their oppositions (p. 189).

Hegel's logic deals with relations among concepts, which bring about the determination of the very concepts that are playing in the game. It is especially the relation of holistic co-determination that by means of an intensional exclusion carry through the conceptual mediation and thus the determinations of the objects through predication, attribution of properties. They find their expression in judgments, in which the determinations of properties can be then further mediated in syllogisms (p. 225).

Berto's conclusion is that Hegel did not aim at denying logical validity to the principles of identity, non-contradiction, and excluded third. What he rather aimed at was overcoming the limits set by the understanding in dealing with the properties of individual substances. Far from being its opposite, Hegel's logic is truly an extension of formal logic and of critical metaphysics in as far as it explicates the gray zone that remains unexpressed by traditional semantics (p. 311).

Too bad, though, that Berto's reduction of dialectic to mere semantics seems to do some injustice to Hegel's original thought, which was not restricted to language and embraces instead actuality as a whole. Dialectic involves an ontological system, it involves also a full fledged philosophy of mind. Berto's book is nonetheless one of the few that provide new insights on Hegel's notions of relation, judgment, determination, and contradiction, which is indeed a great merit, given the dearth of research in a time in which most analytical philosophers do not believe in Hegel.

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